

Platform Design for B2B Ecosystems: The R3-MYDAS Case

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Abstract: Technological platforms are central to modern business ecosystems, enabling firms to orchestrate resources across markets and industries. Platforms leveraging complementarities and network effects support scalable value creation and innovation. Platform design choices are critical to strategic success. To guide these choices, Tura et al. (2016) introduced a foundational framework with four elements: architecture, value creation logic, governance, and competition. As the framework nears its 10th anniversary, this study revisits it in light of significant technological shifts, especially AI, Digital Twins, evolving platform ecosystems, and the growing relevance of B2B contexts. These developments reshape how platforms are designed, governed, and scaled, issues not fully addressed in the original framework. Using a design science approach, we empirically refine the framework within a B2B setting, marked by distinct stakeholders and industrial dynamics. Preliminary findings suggest adding a fifth dimension, "Data and intelligence," and emphasize integrating design elements rather than treating them in isolation.

Keywords:

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